

Explaining Vacuity in Abstract Argumentation

Extended version with all proofs

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Abstract. An abstract argumentation framework is called σ -*vacuous* if it admits no non-empty extension under the semantics σ . We study how vacuity can be explained by examining how subsets of arguments and their induced substructures contribute to it. To this end, we develop a compositional account that traces how vacuity is preserved as arguments are successively added to a framework. Based on this perspective, we study the computational complexity of key tasks for constructing such explanations for admissibility-based semantics.

Keywords. Abstract argumentation, vacuity, explanations

1. Introduction

Abstract argumentation [1] provides a well-established formalism for representing and analysing conflicting information. An *argumentation framework* consists of a set of arguments equipped with a binary attack relation; an attack directed from one argument to another expresses that acceptance of the former undermines (and thus precludes) acceptance of the latter. Accordingly, an argumentation framework is naturally viewed as a directed graph, with arguments as nodes and attacks as directed edges. A *semantics* assigns to such a framework sets of arguments that can be jointly accepted in view of these attacks; these sets are called the *extensions* of the framework under the respective semantics. Different semantics have been proposed [2], and they may yield different sets of extensions for the same framework. Moreover, they may satisfy different formal properties or principles, as studied in principle-based analyses of argumentation semantics [3,4].

Recent work in abstract argumentation has investigated how the acceptability or non-acceptability of arguments can be justified and explained [5,6,7,8,9,10]. While a semantics determines extensions by definition, and thus fixes whether an argument belongs to an extension or not, explanatory approaches aim to identify structural reasons for this membership behaviour. In particular, they seek to point to syntactic features of a framework that enforce or prohibit the acceptance of specific arguments. For instance, Fan and Toni investigate explanations for both the acceptance [5] and the non-acceptance [6] of arguments in abstract argumen-

tation frameworks; their approach characterises explanations either as admissible defence structures supporting an argument, or as minimal structures whose removal would make a previously non-acceptable argument acceptable. Moreover, Brewka *et al.* [11] analyse *strong inconsistency* for generic knowledge representation formalisms (in particular non-monotonic ones), relating *inconsistency*—i. e., the inability to derive valid information—to substructures for which inconsistency persists as they are expanded up to the entire knowledge base. Applying similar ideas to the case of abstract argumentation, Saribatur *et al.* [8] explain non-acceptability of arguments through *strong rejection*: an argument is strongly rejected by a substructure of the argumentation framework if the argument is rejected not only in that substructure, but also in every enclosing structure up to the original framework. The latter two approaches share a similar intuition, namely that there exist substructures that can be singularly seen as responsible for the inability to derive a certain information. It is this singularity that renders both approaches insufficient as a general explanatory vehicle for non-acceptability in argumentation frameworks, as non-acceptability need not be attributable to one single cause, but rather—as we shall see—may emerge from the interaction of multiple substructures. Another explanatory approach, for the problem of explaining acceptability, is that of Bengel and Thimm [12], who provide *sequence-based explanations* for acceptance by constructing extensions step by step, thereby offering an incremental account of how acceptable sets arise. Our approach is most similar in spirit to theirs, although the details of both constructions differ significantly.

In this paper, we focus on a particular form of non-acceptability, namely σ -*vacuity* [13,14]. Given a semantics σ , a framework is σ -vacuous if it admits no non-empty extension under σ ; intuitively, this happens in situations where the attack structure prevents the acceptance of any argument. Such situations may indicate modelling problems, for instance, the presence of self-attacking arguments or cyclic attack patterns. At the same time, vacuity may also arise as a genuine consequence of the interaction between arguments in highly conflicting scenarios. Understanding why a framework is vacuous is therefore important, as it can reveal structural patterns responsible for the absence of acceptable argument sets and help identify those parts of the framework that contribute to this behaviour.

Our aim is to explain σ -vacuity in structural terms by clarifying how interacting substructures give rise to vacuity of the framework as a whole. To this end, we develop a decompositional and incremental account of vacuity. Rather than seeking to identify a single structural cause, we analyse how vacuity is preserved as progressively larger parts of the framework are taken into account; these increments are the building blocks of our explanations. We introduce a measure capturing the granularity of an explanation; smaller values correspond to finer-grained explanatory steps. Finally, we show how enforcing minimality conditions on explanatory steps increases the computational complexity of constructing such explanations.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- Section 3 introduces the notion of *strong vacuity* of a subframework and investigates its usefulness as an explanatory device for vacuity of the entire

framework, characterising structural conditions under which vacuity of a single component extends to the whole.

- In Section 4, we develop *vacuity-preserving decompositions* as an incremental explanation scheme, introduce a measure capturing explanatory granularity, and refine the approach by imposing minimality conditions.
- In Section 5, we analyse the complexity of associated computational tasks, locating the main decision problems for admissibility-based semantics within the polynomial hierarchy and identifying *prefix-minimality* as the source of the higher complexity.

Section 2 introduces the formal preliminaries and Section 6 concludes.

2. Preliminaries

Starting with some finite set of arguments \mathfrak{A} , an argumentation framework [1] is a pair $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ so that $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathfrak{A}$ and $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}$. The relation \mathcal{R} is the *attack relation*: given $a\mathcal{R}b$, we say that a attacks b . For a set of arguments $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ we define $S_F^+ = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid \exists b \in S : b\mathcal{R}a\}$ and $S_F^- = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid \exists b \in S : a\mathcal{R}b\}$. We say that $D \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ defends $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ (in F) iff $S_F^- \subseteq D_F^+$. Given two sets S and S' we suggestively write $S\mathcal{R}S'$ iff $S_F^+ \cap S' \neq \emptyset$; we omit braces for singleton sets, i. e., write $S\mathcal{R}a$ instead of $S\mathcal{R}\{a\}$. The *range* of a set of arguments S is defined as $S_F^\oplus = S \cup S_F^+$. Finally, $\mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ is the set of all argumentation frameworks with arguments in \mathfrak{A} .

Given a framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ and a set of arguments $S \subseteq \mathfrak{A}$, we denote with $F|_S$ the *restriction of F to S* , where $F|_S = (\mathcal{A}_S, \mathcal{R}_S)$, $\mathcal{A}_S = \mathcal{A} \cap S$ and $\mathcal{R}_S = (S \times S) \cap \mathcal{R}$. A framework $F' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ is a *subframework of F* if $\mathcal{A}' \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and $F|_{\mathcal{A}'} = F'$; we write $F' \subseteq F$. Conversely, if $F' \subseteq F$ we also say that F is a *superframework of F'* , and write $F \supseteq F'$.

A *semantics* σ is a mapping $\mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}} \rightarrow 2^{2^{\mathfrak{A}}}$ so that $\sigma(F) \subseteq 2^{\mathfrak{A}}$ for each $F \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, assigning to a framework those argument sets that jointly represent an acceptable point of view in the scenario described by F [1,3]. These jointly acceptable sets of arguments are called the σ -*extensions* of F .

Definition 1. For a framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, we define the semantics:

- $\text{cf}(F) = \{S \subseteq \mathcal{A} \mid S_F^+ \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus S\}$ (*conflict-free*);
- $\text{adm}(F) = \{S \in \text{cf}(F) \mid S_F^- \subseteq S_F^+\}$ (*admissible*);
- $\text{com}(F) = \{S \in \text{adm}(F) \mid \forall a \in \mathcal{A} : \{a\}^- \subseteq S_F^+ \implies a \in S\}$ (*complete*);
- $\text{pr}(F) = \{S \in \text{adm}(F) \mid \nexists S' \in \text{adm}(F) : S \subsetneq S'\}$ (*preferred*);
- $\text{naive}(F) = \{S \in \text{cf}(F) \mid \nexists S' \in \text{cf}(F) : S \subsetneq S'\}$ (*naive*);
- $\text{sstb}(F) = \{S \in \text{com}(F) \mid \nexists S' \in \text{com}(F) : S_F^\oplus \subsetneq S'_F^\oplus\}$ (*semi-stable*).

The following notion of *defence* is fundamental to admissible sets, which are exactly those conflict-free argument sets that defend all their elements.

Definition 2. A semantics σ is *conflict-free* if $\sigma(F) \subseteq \text{cf}(F)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, and it satisfies *defence* if for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ and $S \in \sigma(F)$ we have $S_F^- \subseteq S_F^+$. It satisfies *admissibility* if it satisfies both conflict-freeness and defence.

All semantics from Definition 1 are conflict-free and all except `naive` are admissible.

The following two notions describe the absence of acceptable argument sets.

Definition 3 (Inconsistency). With respect to a semantics σ , a framework F is σ -inconsistent if $\sigma(F) = \emptyset$.

Definition 4 (Vacuity [13,14]). Given a semantics σ , a framework F is σ -vacuous if its σ -extensions contain at most the empty set, i. e., $\sigma(F) \subseteq \{\emptyset\}$.

Example 1. The framework $F = \{(a), \{(a, a)\}\}$ is `adm`-vacuous, but not `adm`-inconsistent, since $\text{adm}(F) = \{\emptyset\}$.

3. Strong Vacuity

In this section, we investigate a strengthened notion of vacuity as a means of tracing the vacuity of a framework to a specific subcomponent. The guiding idea is to capture situations in which a part of the framework enforces vacuity in a way such that the absence of non-empty extensions can be attributed singularly to that component.

Subsection 3.1 introduces the notion formally and situates it within a broader conceptual context. In Subsection 3.2, we analyze a structurally simple case in which the vacuity of a single subframework can be identified as the cause of global vacuity: namely, when an unattacked subframework itself attacks all arguments outside it.

3.1. Strong Inconsistency and Strong Vacuity

We now introduce the notion of *strong inconsistency*; for that, following Brewka *et al.* [11], we define a *logic* in an abstract manner.

Definition 5 (Logic). A *logic* $\mathcal{L} = (\Phi, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{l}, f_{\text{acc}})$ is a quadruple consisting of a set of *well-formed formulas* Φ , a set of *belief sets* \mathbf{B} , an upward-closed¹ set of *inconsistent belief sets* $\mathbf{l} \subseteq \mathbf{B}$, and an *acceptability function* $f_{\text{acc}} : 2^\Phi \rightarrow 2^\mathbf{B}$. A *knowledge base* K of \mathcal{L} is a finite subset of Φ ; K is *inconsistent* iff $f_{\text{acc}}(K) \subseteq \mathbf{l}$.

A strong notion of inconsistency is then defined as follows.

Definition 6. Let $K_0 \subseteq \Phi$. A knowledge base $K \subseteq K_0$ is *strongly K_0 -inconsistent* if for every K' with $K \subseteq K' \subseteq K_0$ we have that $f_{\text{acc}}(K') \subseteq \mathbf{l}$.

We adapt this notion to the knowledge representation formalism of abstract argumentation (as has been done for *inconsistency* in [11]) and specialise it to vacuity as follows: formulas are either arguments $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ or attacks $(a, b) \in \mathfrak{A} \times \mathfrak{A}$. Belief sets are arbitrary sets of arguments, i. e., $\mathbf{B} = 2^\mathfrak{A}$, and we set $\mathbf{l} = \{\emptyset\}$. A knowledge base K then represents an argumentation framework via the mapping

$$\text{AF}(K) = (\mathcal{A}, K \cap (\mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A})) \quad \text{where} \quad \mathcal{A} = K \cap \mathfrak{A},$$

¹A set of sets \mathbb{S} is *upward-closed* iff $S \in \mathbb{S}$ and $S \subseteq S'$ implies $S' \in \mathbb{S}$.

so that, with respect to a semantics σ , the acceptability function becomes $f_{\text{acc}}(K) = \sigma(\text{AF}(K))$. Thus, inconsistent knowledge bases in the terminology of the abstract logic correspond to σ -vacuous argumentation frameworks, and the notion of strong inconsistency then has an immediate analogy in terms of σ -vacuity, as follows.

Definition 7 (Strong Vacuity). Let $F_0 = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ and let σ be a semantics. The framework $F \subseteq F_0$ is *strongly σ -vacuous w.r.t. F_0* if every superframework $F' \supseteq F$ with $F' \subseteq F_0$ is σ -vacuous.

Example 2. Consider the framework (F) in Figure 1, where $F|_{\{a\}}$ consists of the self-attacking argument a and thus is **adm**-vacuous; it is not **adm**-inconsistent, since the empty set remains admissible in every framework. Expanding $F|_{\{a\}}$ by incorporating arguments b and c , we find that in fact every superframework of $F|_{\{a\}}$, up to F , is **adm**-vacuous; thus, $F|_{\{a\}}$ is strongly **adm**-vacuous.

Figure 1. This framework contains a minimal strongly vacuous subframework.

Saribatur *et al.* [8] introduce the related notion of *strong rejection*, which concerns the persistent non-acceptability of a single argument under expansion.

Definition 8. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be a semantics, let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, and let $a \in \mathcal{A}$. The subframework $F|_S$ *strongly rejects a w.r.t. F under σ* if for each $S' \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ with $S \subseteq S'$ we have $a \notin \bigcup \sigma(F|_{S'})$.

Example 3. In the framework (F) of Figure 1, the subframework $F|_{\{a\}}$ strongly rejects all of a, b, c .

Strong vacuity is in fact equivalent to strong rejection of every argument.

Proposition 1. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be a semantics, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. The subframework $F|_S$ is strongly σ -vacuous w.r.t. F iff $F|_S$ strongly rejects every $a \in \mathcal{A}$ w.r.t. F under σ .

Proof. For any $S' \supseteq S$, $\sigma(F|_{S'}) \subseteq \{\emptyset\}$ iff no argument occurs in any σ -extension of $F|_{S'}$, i.e., iff every $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is strongly rejected w.r.t. F under σ . \square

3.2. Vacuity in Unattacked Subframeworks

Example 2 illustrates how vacuity of a subframework may carry over to the full framework: a subframework that is vacuous in isolation may force every enclosing framework to remain vacuous as well. We now study this for unattacked vacuous subframeworks, assuming that every framework with a non-empty admissible set also has a non-empty σ -extension. The following notion captures this condition.

Definition 9. A semantics σ is *adm-responsive* if, for any framework $F \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, $\sigma(F) \not\subseteq \{\emptyset\}$ whenever $\text{adm}(F) \not\subseteq \{\emptyset\}$.

Lemma 1. *adm*, *pr*, *com*, *sstb*, and *naive* are *adm-responsive*.

Proof. Immediate for *adm*. For *pr* and *naive*, every non-empty admissible (resp. conflict-free) set extends to a maximal one. For *com* and *sstb*, the existence of a non-empty admissible set yields a non-empty complete extension, excluding \emptyset as maximal range. \square

In the following, let $\mathbb{U}(F) = \{U \subseteq \mathcal{A} \mid (\mathcal{A} \setminus U)_F^+ \cap U = \emptyset\}$ be the *unattacked* argument sets, i. e., sets of arguments that are not attacked from outside.

Proposition 2. Let σ be an *adm-responsive* semantics that satisfies admissibility, and let F be a σ -vacuous framework. Then for any $U \in \mathbb{U}(F)$, $F|_U$ is σ -vacuous as well.

Proof. If $E \in \sigma(F|_U)$ is non-empty for some $U \in \mathbb{U}(F)$, then E is admissible in F , so by *adm-responsiveness*, F is not σ -vacuous. \square

We then ask when vacuity of an unattacked subframework implies vacuity of the entire framework.

Proposition 3. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be a semantics that satisfies *adm-responsiveness* and admissibility, and let $U \in \mathbb{U}(F)$ so that $(\mathcal{A} \setminus U) \subseteq U_F^+$. If $F|_U$ is σ -vacuous, then so is F .

Proof. Since every argument in $\mathcal{A} \setminus U$ is attacked by U and undefended, any $E \in \sigma(F)$ satisfies $E \subseteq U$. If F had a non-empty extension E , then E would also be admissible in $F|_U$, contradicting σ -vacuity of $F|_U$ by *adm-responsiveness*. \square

The above result shows that, in the particular case of an unattacked vacuous subframework, it is sufficient for the subframework to attack all of its surrounding arguments for vacuity to carry over to the entire framework.

Example 4. In the framework (F) of Figure 1, we have $\{a\} \in \mathbb{U}(F)$, and a attacks both b and c . Consequently, F is $\{\text{adm}, \text{pr}, \text{com}, \text{sstb}\}$ -vacuous. Since *naive* does not satisfy admissibility, we cannot infer vacuity of F for that semantics; and indeed, both $\{b\}$ and $\{c\}$ are *naive* extensions of F .

The unattacked and vacuous subframeworks of Proposition 3 that attack all of their surroundings are actually strongly vacuous. Indeed, attacking all (not self-attacking) surrounding arguments is necessary for strong vacuity.²

Proposition 4. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be an *adm-responsive* semantics, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. If $F|_S$ is strongly σ -vacuous, then either $a\mathcal{R}a$ or $S\mathcal{R}a$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus S$.

Proof. If $a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus S$ is neither self-attacking, nor attacked from S , then a is admissible in $F|_{S \cup \{a\}}$, thus $\sigma(F|_{S \cup \{a\}}) \not\subseteq \{\emptyset\}$. \square

²Saribatur *et al.* state a similar proposition w.r.t. strong rejection of single arguments under admissible and grounded semantics [8].

Propositions 3 and 4 characterise strong vacuity of unattacked subframeworks as follows.

Corollary 1. Let $F \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be an adm-responsive semantics that satisfies admissibility, and let $S \in \mathbb{U}(F)$. The subframework $F|_S$ is strongly σ -vacuous iff it is σ -vacuous, and $S\mathcal{R}a$ or $a\mathcal{R}a$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus S$.

For unattacked subframeworks, strong vacuity imposes a highly restrictive structural condition: the vacuous component must attack every non-self-attacking argument outside it. This limitation is of course the immediate consequence of wanting to attribute global vacuity to one singular cause, and it motivates the more general decompositional account developed next.

4. Vacuity-Preserving Decompositions

The approach taken in this section is inspired by *serialisability* [15] for admissibility-based semantics, where extensions are constructed stepwise, by selecting *initial sets* (i. e., \subseteq -minimal, non-empty admissible sets [16]), removing them together with the arguments they attack, and continuing on the remaining framework. In a similar spirit, we analyse vacuity incrementally: starting from a \subseteq -minimal vacuous subframework, we successively add arguments and their induced attacks while requiring vacuity to be preserved at every stage. This yields *vacuity-preserving decompositions* as a formal account of stepwise explanations of vacuity (Section 4.1); Section 4.2 then refines this account by imposing minimality conditions on the increments.

4.1. Definition and Basic Properties

We now show how a vacuous framework can be decomposed so as to yield a stepwise explanation of vacuity.

Definition 10 (Decomposition of a framework). Let σ be a semantics and let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ be σ -vacuous. A σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition of F is a finite sequence $\langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ of pairwise disjoint, non-empty subsets of \mathcal{A} , such that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i = \mathcal{A}$, and for $1 \leq i \leq n$, $\sigma(F|_{S_i}) \subseteq \{\emptyset\}$ where $S_i = \bigcup_{j=1}^i G_j$.

A σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition of a framework partitions its argument set into components, so that σ -vacuity is preserved as the framework is stepwise assembled along the decomposition.

Example 5. The framework in Figure 2 admits the following adm-vacuity-preserving decompositions: $D_1 = \langle \{d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{e\} \rangle$, $D_2 = \langle \{d\}, \{a, b, c, e\} \rangle$, $D_3 = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle$, $D_4 = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{e\}, \{d\} \rangle$, $D_5 = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d, e\} \rangle$, $D_6 = \langle \{a, b, c, d, e\} \rangle$.

Intuitively, smaller components provide finer explanations, motivating the following measure.

Figure 2. This framework admits several vacuity-preserving decompositions.

Definition 11. For a sequence of sets $D = \langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$, we define its *width*

$$|D|_{\max} = \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} |G_i|.$$

For the empty sequence, we set $|\langle \rangle|_{\max} = 0$.

Applied to a σ -vacuity preserving decomposition of F , its width measures the size of the largest component that must be added at once in order to preserve vacuity. We will refer to this measure as the σ -*vacuity width* of the decomposition.

Example 6. Using the designations from Example 5, we have $|D_1|_{\max} = 3$, $|D_2|_{\max} = 4$, $|D_3|_{\max} = |D_4|_{\max} = |D_5|_{\max} = 3$, and $|D_6|_{\max} = 5$.

In what follows, we often consider decompositions not of the whole argument set, but relative to a fixed initial component. This reflects the incremental nature of our approach: at each stage, vacuity is evaluated with respect to the arguments already introduced.

Definition 12 (Decomposition with respect to a prefix). Let σ be a semantics, let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ be σ -vacuous, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is σ -vacuous. A σ -*vacuity-preserving decomposition* of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ is a finite (and possibly empty) sequence $\langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ of pairwise disjoint, non-empty subsets of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$, such that $\langle S, G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ is a σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition of F when $S \neq \emptyset$, and $\langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ is such a decomposition when $S = \emptyset$.

Example 7. Going back to the framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ in Figure 2, we find that the non-empty and strict *adm*-vacuous subframeworks of F are induced by $S_1 = \{d\}$ and $S_2 = \{a, b, c\}$. Both $D'_1 = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{e\} \rangle$ and $D'_2 = \langle \{a, b, c, e\} \rangle$ are *adm*-vacuity-preserving decompositions of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S_1$, and $D'_3 = \langle \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle$, $D'_4 = \langle \{e\}, \{d\} \rangle$, $D'_5 = \langle \{d, e\} \rangle$ are *adm*-vacuity-preserving decompositions of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S_2$.

Our construction relates to strong vacuity (Definition 7) as follows.

Corollary 2. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be a framework, σ a semantics, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is σ -vacuous. Then $F|_S$ is strongly σ -vacuous if and only if every ordered partition of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ into pairwise disjoint, non-empty subsets is a σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$.

Given a vacuous prefix S , we measure the width of decompositions extending S to the full framework.

Definition 13 (Vacuity width relative to a prefix). Let σ be a semantics so that $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ is σ -vacuous, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Provided $F|_S$ is vacuous, the σ -vacuity width of F relative to S is the minimum width over all σ -vacuity-preserving decompositions of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$.

Example 8. Continuing Example 7, we find $|D'_1|_{\max} = 3$ and $|D'_2|_{\max} = 4$, so that the adm-vacuity width of F relative to S_1 is 3. Moreover, we have that $|D'_3|_{\max} = |D'_4|_{\max} = 1$ and $|D'_5|_{\max} = 2$, therefore the adm-vacuity width of F relative to S_2 is 1.

Corollary 3. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, and let σ be a semantics. If $F|_S$ is strongly σ -vacuous, then the σ -vacuity width of F relative to S is at most 1.

The next proposition establishes a monotonicity property of vacuity width relative to a prefix under restriction to unattacked parts: restricting to such parts cannot increase the width, so they provide local lower bounds on the granularity of explanations in the full framework.

Proposition 5. Let σ be an adm-responsive semantics that satisfies admissibility. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ be σ -vacuous, let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ so that $F|_S$ is σ -vacuous, and let $U \in \mathbb{U}(F)$. Then the σ -vacuity width of F relative to S is greater or equal to the σ -vacuity width of $F|_U$ relative to $S \cap U$.

Proof. Let $D = \langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ be a σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$, and for each $1 \leq i \leq n$ define $H_i = G_i \cap U$. Remove empty sets from the sequence $\langle H_1, \dots, H_n \rangle$ and denote the resulting sequence by D_U . Since the G_i are pairwise disjoint, so are the non-empty H_i , and their union is

$$\bigcup_i H_i = \left(\bigcup_i G_i \right) \cap U = (\mathcal{A} \setminus S) \cap U = U \setminus S.$$

Hence D_U is a partition of $U \setminus S$. Now let $T_i = (S \cap U) \cup \bigcup_{j \leq i} H_j$ be a prefix induced by D_U . By construction,

$$T_i = U \cap \left(S \cup \bigcup_{j \leq i} G_j \right).$$

Since D is σ -vacuity-preserving, $F|_{S \cup \bigcup_{j \leq i} G_j}$ is σ -vacuous. As $U \in \mathbb{U}(F)$, the set $U \cap (S \cup \bigcup_{j \leq i} G_j)$ is unattacked in that prefix framework as well. Therefore, by Proposition 2, its restriction $F|_{T_i}$ is σ -vacuous. Thus every prefix of D_U is σ -vacuous, so D_U is a σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition of $U \setminus S$ in $F|_U$. Finally, for every i we have $|H_i| \leq |G_i|$, hence $|D_U|_{\max} \leq |D|_{\max}$. Since D was arbitrary, taking the minimum over all σ -vacuity-preserving decompositions of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ yields the claim. \square

The final example in this subsection shows how a vacuity-preserving decomposition can be used to explain vacuity, proceeding stepwise along the members of the decomposition sequence.

Example 9. Let us explain the adm-vacuity of the framework (F) in Figure 2, starting with $S = \{d\}$ and a decomposition $D = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{e\} \rangle$. First, $F|_S$ is vacuous since d attacks itself. Second, assuming vacuity of the odd cycle $\{a, b, c\}$ is established, d cannot defend any argument as it is not conflict-free. Third, e fails to defend against all attacks, so cannot contribute to any admissible set.

4.2. Minimality

For explanatory purposes, it is natural to focus on substructures that are vacuous in isolation and on increments that are minimal relative to a given prefix. We formalise these notions below.

Definition 14 (Minimal vacuity). Given a semantics σ , a non-empty framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ ($\mathcal{A} \neq \emptyset$) is *minimally σ -vacuous* if it is σ -vacuous, and no non-empty, strict subframework $F|_S$ with $\emptyset \neq S \subsetneq \mathcal{A}$ is σ -vacuous.

Example 10. In the framework (F) of Figure 2, $F|_{\{a,b,c\}}$ as well as $F|_{\{d\}}$ are minimally adm-vacuous.

The second notion concerns minimality of increments relative to a prefix: to identify only the relevant elements of an explanation, each increment should be minimal relative to the current prefix.

Definition 15. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be a semantics, let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is σ -vacuous, and let $G \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus S$. We say that $F|_G$ is *prefix-minimally σ -vacuous with respect to F and S* if $F|_{S \cup G}$ is σ -vacuous, and $F|_{S \cup G'}$ is not σ -vacuous for any $\emptyset \subsetneq G' \subsetneq G$.

Example 11. In the framework (F) from Figure 2, $F|_{\{d\}}$ is prefix-minimally adm-vacuous with respect to F and $\{a, b, c\}$. At the same time, $F|_{\{a,b,c\}}$ is prefix-minimally adm-vacuous with respect to F and $\{d\}$.

Definitions 13 and 14 together give rise to the following notion.

Definition 16 (Vacuity width of a framework). For a semantics σ and a σ -vacuous framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, the *σ -vacuity width of F* is the minimal σ -vacuity width of F with respect to S , taken over all minimally σ -vacuous prefixes $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

Thus if the σ -vacuity width of F is k , then every explanation of its vacuity that starts from a minimally σ -vacuous prefix must contain a step in which at least k arguments are introduced simultaneously.

The minimal vacuous subframeworks provide natural starting points for an explanation of vacuity. From there, we seek decompositions that are not only width-minimal—since width reflects only the largest increment—but whose steps are prefix-minimally vacuous with respect to their prefixes. Requiring this for every step in the decomposition yields the following notion.

Definition 17. Let σ be a semantics, let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$ be σ -vacuous, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is σ -vacuous. A σ -vacuity-preserving decomposition $\langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ is *prefix-minimal* if for each G_i , $F|_{G_i}$ is prefix-minimally σ -vacuous with respect to F and $S \cup G_1 \cup \dots \cup G_{i-1}$.

A vacuity-preserving decomposition can always be rendered prefix-minimal.

Proposition 6. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, let σ be a semantics, and let $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is σ -vacuous. Every non-empty $G \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus S$ for which $F|_{S \cup G}$ is σ -vacuous contains a non-empty subset $G' \subseteq G$ so that $F|_{G'}$ is prefix-minimally σ -vacuous with respect to F and S .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{X} = \{H \subseteq G \mid H \neq \emptyset \text{ and } \sigma(F|_{S \cup H}) \subseteq \{\emptyset\}\}$. Since $G \in \mathcal{X}$, the set is non-empty and finite, hence has a \subseteq -minimal element G' . Then $G' \neq \emptyset$, $F|_{S \cup G'}$ is σ -vacuous, and no non-empty proper subset of G' is vacuous, i.e., $F|_{G'}$ is prefix-minimally σ -vacuous with respect to F and S . \square

Vacuity-preserving decompositions explain vacuity by tracing how it persists along successive steps. Width captures the size of the largest increment, i.e., the most complex explanatory step, while prefix-minimality isolates those increments that are essential at each stage. Our decompositions also admit a temporal interpretation: arguments are revealed stepwise, and vacuity must persist throughout.

5. Computational Complexity

We now turn to the computational complexity of constructing explanations. We assume familiarity with basic complexity theory and the polynomial hierarchy; for an introduction, see [17]. We begin by recalling the following result due to Dvořák and Dunne [18] for the semantics relevant to our setting.

Proposition 7. Determining whether a framework F admits a nonempty σ -extension is NP-complete for $\sigma \in \{\text{adm}, \text{pr}, \text{com}, \text{sstb}\}$.

The following decision problems are relevant to our approach.

Problem 1 (VPD-VERIFY). Given a framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, decide whether a decomposition $\langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ is σ -vacuity-preserving.

Problem 2 (PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY). Given a framework $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, a prefix $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, and an increment $G \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus S$, decide whether $F|_G$ is prefix-minimally σ -vacuous with respect to F and S .

Problem 3 (WIDTH). Given a framework F and an integer $k \geq 0$, decide whether F is σ -vacuous and the σ -vacuity width of F is at most k .

Problem 4 (STRONG-VACUOUS-VERIFY). Given frameworks F_0 and $F \subseteq F_0$, decide whether F is strongly σ -vacuous with respect to F_0 .

Problem 5 (MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY). Decide whether a framework is minimally σ -vacuous.

Proposition 8. The complexity of the above problems for the case $\sigma = \text{adm}$ is located within the polynomial hierarchy as follows.

1. VPD-VERIFY is coNP-complete for $\sigma = \text{adm}$.

2. PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY is coNP-hard and belongs to Π_2^P , for $\sigma = \text{adm}$.
3. WIDTH is coNP-hard and belongs to Σ_3^P , for $\sigma = \text{adm}$.
4. STRONG-VACUOUS-VERIFY is coNP-complete for $\sigma = \text{adm}$.
5. MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY belongs to Π_2^P , for $\sigma = \text{adm}$.

Proof of Proposition 8.1. Consider $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, an initial prefix $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, and a decomposition $D = \langle G_1, \dots, G_n \rangle$ of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$, and let $S_i = S \cup \bigcup_{j \leq i} G_j$. The sequence D is *not* vacuity-preserving if there exists an index $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $F|_{S_i}$ is non-vacuous. A corresponding witness is a pair (i, T) so that $T \in \text{adm}(F|_{S_i})$, and verification of such witness can be done in polynomial time. Hence the complement problem lies in NP, and the original problem is in coNP.

For coNP-hardness, deciding whether F is adm-vacuous is already coNP-hard. This reduces to the present problem by taking a single block $G_1 = \mathcal{A} \setminus S$. \square

Proof of Proposition 8.2. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\mathfrak{A}}$, $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, and $G \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus S$. Consider the complement problem: $F|_G$ is *not* prefix-minimally adm-vacuous iff either

- (i) $F|_{S \cup G}$ is not adm-vacuous, or
- (ii) there exists a non-empty $H \subsetneq G$ such that $F|_{S \cup H}$ is adm-vacuous.

(i) is in NP, witnessed by a non-empty admissible set in $F|_{S \cup G}$. For (ii), guess such an H and universally verify that no non-empty admissible set T exists in $F|_{S \cup H}$; this yields a $\exists H \forall T$ predicate with polynomial-time check (verifying admissibility of T), hence (ii) is in Σ_2^P . Since $\text{NP} \subseteq \Sigma_2^P$, both (i) and (ii) are in Σ_2^P , and since Σ_2^P is closed under union, the entire complement problem lies in Σ_2^P , so that the original problem belongs to Π_2^P .

For hardness, we reduce from the problem of deciding whether a framework is adm-vacuous, as follows: consider the framework $F' = (\mathcal{A} \cup \{x\}, \mathcal{R} \cup \{(x, x)\})$ with $x \notin \mathcal{A}$. Set $S = \mathcal{A}$ and $G = \{x\}$. Then $F'|_{S \cup G} = F'$ is adm-vacuous iff F is adm-vacuous, since x is self-attacking and no attack exists between x and \mathcal{A} . As G is a singleton, the minimality condition holds trivially. This construction yields a polynomial-time reduction from adm-vacuity, establishing coNP-hardness. \square

Proof of Proposition 8.3. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and let $k \geq 0$. F is adm-vacuous and the adm-vacuity width of F is at most k iff there exists a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is minimally adm-vacuous and there exists an adm-vacuity-preserving decomposition D of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ with $|D|_{\max} \leq k$. Thus the problem has the form

$$\exists S \exists D : p(F, S, D, k),$$

where $p(F, S, D, k)$ expresses that:

- (i) $F|_S$ is minimally adm-vacuous;
- (ii) D is a sequence of pairwise disjoint, non-empty subsets partitioning $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$;
- (iii) $|G_i| \leq k$ for all i ;
- (iv) for each prefix $S_i = S \cup \bigcup_{j \leq i} G_j$ we have $\text{adm}(F|_{S_i}) \subseteq \{\emptyset\}$.

Condition (i) is precisely MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY and belongs to Π_2^P . Conditions (ii) and (iii) can be verified in polynomial time. Condition (iv) is precisely VPD-VERIFY and belongs to coNP . Since $\text{P} \subseteq \text{coNP} \subseteq \Pi_2^P$ and Π_2^P is closed under conjunction of Π_2^P predicates, the resulting predicate p is in Π_2^P . The decision problem is therefore expressible as an existential quantifier followed by a Π_2^P predicate, placing it in Σ_3^P .

For coNP -hardness, we reduce from the problem of deciding adm -vacuity, and take $k = |\mathcal{A}|$. We show: F is adm -vacuous and adm -vacuity width of F is at most $|\mathcal{A}|$ iff F is adm -vacuous. (\Rightarrow) There exists a minimally adm -vacuous $F|_S$ together with an adm -vacuity-preserving decomposition of $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$. Thus F is adm -vacuous. (\Leftarrow) Every finite adm -vacuous framework F has a minimally adm -vacuous subframework $F|_S$, and the trivial decomposition $G = \langle \mathcal{A} \setminus S \rangle$ has width $|G|_{\max} = |\mathcal{A} \setminus S| \leq |\mathcal{A}|$. \square

Proof of Proposition 8.4. Let $F_0 = (\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{R}_0) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\text{all}}$ and let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \subseteq F_0$. By Definition 7, F is *not* strongly adm -vacuous w.r.t. F_0 if there exists a superframework F' with $F \subseteq F' \subseteq F_0$ such that $\text{adm}(F') \not\subseteq \{\emptyset\}$. A witness for the complement problem is therefore a pair (S, T) where $\mathcal{A} \subseteq S \subseteq \mathcal{A}_0$ and $\emptyset \neq T \subseteq S$ such that $T \in \text{adm}(F_0|_S)$. Verification of (S, T) can be done in polynomial time: one checks $\mathcal{A} \subseteq S \subseteq \mathcal{A}_0$, constructs $F_0|_S$, and checks that T is admissible in that framework. Hence the complement problem lies in NP , and the original problem belongs to coNP .

For coNP -hardness, the reduction from adm -vacuity is straightforward: a framework is adm -vacuous iff it is strongly adm -vacuous w.r.t. itself. \square

Proof of Proposition 8.5. Let $F = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}) \in \mathfrak{F}_{\text{all}}$. The complement problem states: F is *not* minimally vacuous iff either

- (i) F is not adm -vacuous; or
- (ii) there exists a non-empty $S \subsetneq \mathcal{A}$ such that $F|_S$ is adm -vacuous.

For (i), guess a non-empty admissible set in F (in NP). For (ii), guess S and universally verify that no subset $\emptyset \neq T \subseteq S$ is admissible. This yields a $\exists S \forall T$ predicate with polynomial time check, hence (ii) is in Σ_2^P . Since $\text{NP} \subseteq \Sigma_2^P$ and Σ_2^P is closed under union, the entire complement problem lies in Σ_2^P and the original problem belongs to Π_2^P . \square

For PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY we obtain coNP -hardness and membership in Π_2^P ; for MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY we currently only obtain membership in Π_2^P . Whether either problem is Π_2^P -complete remains open.³ Observe that MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY is a special case of PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY (take $S = \emptyset$ and $G = \mathcal{A}$), so any hardness result for MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY will immediately transfer to PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY.

Regarding the construction of explanations, the computational hardness does not arise from checking vacuity itself—decidable in coNP —but from enforcing

³In particular, showing that either problem is even NP -hard has proven elusive, since they deal with *non*-existence of (non-empty) extensions; however, Π_2^P -membership is also the best upper bound we could find.

prefix-minimality. The latter requires quantification over all strict subincrements, thereby lifting the problem to the second level of the polynomial hierarchy.

A note on generality. The above membership arguments depend only on the complexity of deciding whether a framework admits a non-empty σ -extension. If this underlying decision problem belongs to some complexity class C , then the same reasoning yields corresponding upper bounds expressed relative to an oracle access to C : VPD-VERIFY and STRONG-VACUOUS-VERIFY lie in coNP^C , PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY and MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY lie in $\Pi_2^{P,C}$, and WIDTH lies in $\Sigma_3^{P,C}$. Here $\Pi_2^{P,C}$ and $\Sigma_3^{P,C}$ denote the second resp. third level of the polynomial hierarchy with oracle access to C , meaning that machines at this level may query the non-emptiness decision problem as an oracle in addition to their usual polynomial-time and NP-type reasoning.

For the semantics of interest to us, Proposition 7 establishes that non-emptiness of σ -extensions has the same complexity as for adm ; together with the constructions above, this yields the identical bounds.

Proposition 9. For $\sigma \in \{\text{adm}, \text{pr}, \text{com}, \text{sstb}\}$, we have that both VPD-VERIFY and STRONG-VACUOUS-VERIFY lie in coNP , PREFIX-MINIMAL-VERIFY and MIN-VACUOUS-VERIFY lie in Π_2^P , and WIDTH lies in Σ_3^P .

6. Discussion

In this paper, we introduced vacuity-preserving decompositions as a compositional and incremental framework for explaining σ -vacuity in abstract argumentation. Rather than attributing vacuity to a single substructure, our approach captures how vacuity emerges from the interaction of multiple components by tracing its preservation along a sequence of argument additions. We defined vacuity width as a measure that quantifies the granularity of such explanations and analysed its structural properties, including its relation to strong vacuity and its behaviour under restriction to unattacked subframeworks. We further refined the framework by introducing minimality conditions on explanatory steps, ensuring that each increment captures an essential contribution to vacuity. Finally, we investigated the computational complexity of constructing such explanations for admissibility-based semantics, showing that while basic verification tasks lie at the first level of the polynomial hierarchy, enforcing minimality raises the complexity to the second and third level.

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